

ACADEMIC RELATED VALUES-ORIENTED SKILLS DEMONSTRATED DURING PANDEMIC

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ABSTRACT

Values are said to be norms of an individual which becomes a guide in choosing right from wrong. It is either innate or acquired by an individual which slowly develops with interactions from the family, community and society. However, human interactions have been lately hampered due to the covid-19 pandemic, socialization and gatherings have been altered, and in some way or the other may have greatly affect the behavior of people particularly the school children, the learners in general. The academic and values skills that schools taught may be haltered which would likely cause a deterrence to the development of a growing child whose holistic well-being are half-way on the hands of our educational system. With the effects brought about by the Covid-19, the Department of Education ensured that students will not be greatly affected by this pandemic. The study investigates the academic related values-oriented skills demonstrated by the junior high school learners during pandemic. The responses were accumulated through online survey from the 60 respondents from junior high school to determine the learners academic related values-oriented skills during pandemic. The findings suggest that there is no significant difference in the academic related values-oriented skills among the grade levels of the junior high school as well as their gender however, findings showed that there is a significant difference between males and females in terms of managing tasks on time. The implication of the result suggests a need to maintain and reinforce other values-oriented skills in the teaching learning process despite the covid-19 pandemic.

Keywords: COVID-19 Pandemic, Values-oriented skills, Values, Junior High school, Zamboanga city, Philippines